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PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF GLOBAL, REGIONAL AND LOCAL PROBLEMS OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE

Ghulomov Akramjon Bakhromovich

Fergana State University

Faculty of History, Department of Philosophy

Senior teacher of philosophy

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in

Rakhmatova Rukhshona

Fergana State University

Her student is

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12177262>

Abstract: This article shows that in the conditions of current globalization, it is impossible to realize the potential possibility of humanity to achieve a common goal outside the framework of the ecological imperative. After all, the historical necessity of the integration of civilizations requires an institutional system of global management of international environmental political relations. In other words, "the process of globalization requires the mobilization of civilizational resources of various communities, including the active participation of newly independent countries in this process, and the need to solve the global problems that have arisen has been highlighted.

Key words: tradition, civilizations, integration, historical necessity, international ecological political relations, ecological thinking, ecological outlook, social existence, social consciousness, science and technology, ecological culture, ecological policy.

INTRODUCTION

A new political worldview and ecological thinking were formed in the history of humanity in the 20th century. This is gaining great importance in the mutual cooperation and relations of the scientists of the world in terms of nature protection and solving environmental problems. Two perils hang over humanity. These are nuclear and ecological disasters. The new worldview is aimed at completely eliminating these two dangers from the history of mankind. This should ultimately free humanity from the problem of self-destruction. The activity, power, and practical importance of the new way of thinking, its unique aspects, are seen in this way. After all, "a person creates his own destiny with his own hands, work and ability, tireless effort and patience." At the same time, he destroys everything with his own hands.

Ecological culture as a complex and diverse phenomenon affects all spheres of social life. In turn, it is difficult to improve any sphere of society's life without the

development of ecological culture. Such a situation shows the social nature of ecological culture, the social determination of its development. Therefore, only a concrete-historical approach to ecological culture allows for a correct understanding of its essence.

The task of regulating ecological culture is clearly seen in rituals and traditions. Of course, any cultural norm can emerge as a factor regulating his activity only if it becomes an inner belief of a person. Therefore, we can learn how much the population has mastered the norms of ecological culture by looking at how they behave in different situations. So, regulation of people's activities, communication, formation of lifestyle, subordinating social relations to certain norms is one of the important features of culture.

Elimination of environmental problems and formation of environmental culture is a long-term process. In this sense, the development of the theoretical methodology of the problem of ecological culture is important. The following should be recognized as an important task in the development of a new theoretical methodology for the scientific analysis of the history of modern ecological culture:

- improvement of the methodology of studying ecological culture;
- studying the historical stages of the genesis and formation of ecological culture and developing theoretical, practical and methodological recommendations for its development;
- to determine the functional importance of ecological culture in the development of society;
- in the development of ecological cultural heritage, it is to show succession relations and methods of its development.

In the conditions of current globalization, it is shown that the potential possibility of achieving the common goal of mankind cannot be realized outside the framework of the ecological imperative. After all, the historical necessity of the integration of civilizations requires an institutional system of global management of international environmental political relations. In other words, "the process of globalization requires the mobilization of civilizational resources of various communities, including the active participation of newly independent states in this process, and maintains the necessity that emerging global problems can be solved only together. This is a new way of dialogue of civilizations and international cultural relations.

Globalization of environmental problems is an objective process by its nature. Because nature knows no boundaries and forms a single ecosystem. That

is why the activities of official international environmental organizations, as well as various industrial corporations, are becoming secular. Of course, this process has both positive and negative aspects. Usually, the criterion of development is emphasized as integrative diversity. Globalization reinforces integrative tendencies. If the diversity of the social system does not decrease, this is a positive sign. Such a situation is observed today in nature and society, of course.

In the course of historical development, global and regional environmental problems have arisen under the influence of human activity. Environmental problems can be classified based on territorial, geographical, climatic, national and other principles. Global environmental problems are understood as problems that concern all regions of the world and are faced by all mankind. These include health care, treatment of serious diseases, nature conservation, climate change, urbanization, further exploration of the world's oceans, meeting the growing population's demand for food, energy and resources, and more. . From this point of view, environmental problems are divided into regional and local problems depending on the scale.

Today, as a result of the strengthening of integration relations and the acceleration of globalization, environmental problems are becoming global and their form is increasing day by day. In recent years, the problem of air pollution and climate change has emerged as one of the most painful global environmental problems. Also, today humanity is threatened by global environmental risks, such as the depletion of fresh water reserves, the drying up of the Aral Sea, the erosion of arable land, the cutting of forests, the loss of biological diversity, and the merciless pollution of rivers, seas and oceans. Such deficiencies have a negative impact on the environment and lead to a violation of the ecological balance. These are the reasons that worsen not only the natural environment, but also the social environment. In our everyday life, local ecological problems are often caused by gross violation of ecological norms and standards, low level of ecological culture. Cleanliness of air, water, and soil plays an important role in the health and sustainable development of all creatures in the world. We can see that there are local environmental problems specific to all three natural phenomena on the scale of our country. Also, it is not difficult to perceive and understand the negative results of the pressure of the citizens of our country on the environment from statistical data.

At the current stage of historical development of human civilization, a number of social, economic and spiritual problems are gaining special importance. In order to solve them, the world community should mobilize all its

capabilities. The environmental protection policy of states that have gained political sovereignty should be directed to finding ways to eliminate the consequences of the disastrous ecological situation inherited from the authoritarian system. In a word, the state, with the help of social, economic and political factors, allows to eliminate the threat of large-scale environmental stress, to create an economically clean living environment necessary for the birth and development of a physically healthy young generation. The essential vital interests of a person include providing optimal environmental conditions for human activity, protecting the health of the population, establishing a stable ecological situation in the vital and essential interests of society, ensuring the health of the population, and forming a healthy generation. The vital interests of the society include stable development, stability of the environmental situation in the world, formation of a healthy lifestyle, ensuring a high level of scientific and technical development in the leading sectors of the economy, and creating an effective system of national security .

At the current stage of world development, issues related to ecology, the expansion of natural ecosystem degradation, the reduction of biological diversity, the threat of global appropriation of the natural environment, the destruction of industrial facilities, the impact of economic and other activities on the environment and the living of the population. the impact has worried the world community. If the influence of man on nature, his own power, causes the opposite effect of nature on humanity. With this, it creates complex, multifaceted and diverse problems. An ecological threat arises in a certain geographical area and has an escalation.

Environmental problems are one of today's global, urgent social problems that cannot be stopped. Undoubtedly, solving this problem will determine the future of all peoples and nations. This world community is in constant motion today. The problem of environmental problems has gone out of the national and domestic sphere and has become a common problem of all mankind.

In fact, the processes of interaction between humanity and nature, which have been formed and developed for millions of years, are now entering a highly conflicting stage. "Living or life is a continuous series of compromises. Today, the conflict between nature and man is coming to the fore. It was at this time that a new compromise was needed."

In the history of mankind, a number of problems related to the interaction of man and nature appeared, the solution of which was not as complex as it is today. Many events that took place in the world in the middle of the 20th

century led to a change in the attitude of man to nature. Achieving high peaks in economic development led to the creation of a natural environment. The inextricable connection between modern civilization and environmental protection was forgotten in the era, and irrevocable ecological problems have appeared in the form of chasing. If we carelessly treat the natural disasters that are happening today, no one can guarantee that the same thing will happen in our region tomorrow.

With the development of society, the impact of people on the environment increases. Man interacts with nature, i.e. with flora and fauna, underground and surface resources. In today's era, when environmental problems are expanding and solving them has become an urgent task, the role of ecological awareness and ecological culture is incomparable for humanity in solving these problems. Of course, as a result of scientific and technical development, the development of science and technology in various fields, the emergence of new energy sources and chemical substances, as a result of the evil use of natural resources, the air and water become polluted, the land that feeds humanity becomes unusable, and as a result, it deprives it of its living environment. At the present time, humanity has realized what danger it is facing, and clearly felt the consequences of the damage caused by human activities to the environment. As a result of the influence of human activity, significant changes are taking place in the environment. These were mainly in the current classification of environmental security: global, regional, national, local environmental security did not go beyond the territory of our country.

Such global environmental issues can include:

- problems of the azan layer, i.e. erosion;
- climate change;
- desertification;
- lack of clean drinking water;
- the problem of the island sea;
- reduction of animal and plant species;
- illegal cutting of flora;
- land degradation;
- shortage of water resources;
- atmospheric pollution is one of them.

Man, being a part of nature, has discovered the laws of nature in order to protect nature and regulate its rational use through the relationship with it, due

to the formation of ecological culture. But man, through his influence on nature, disturbed its balance and disrupted the periodic balance of natural phenomena.

The change of social consciousness, the development of spiritual culture in an ecological direction on the basis of attitudes towards values, the formation of a new outlook on the life of our planet is a long and difficult process, and in this place ecological culture is of particular importance.

At the same time that a number of achievements are being made in the formation of ecological culture, formation and development of ecological consciousness and worldview, we should pay attention to school education, secondary and higher educational institutions, which play an important role in inculcating this field.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. From national revival to national rise. 4-wire – Tashkent: Uzbekistan.
2. Deryabin V. A., Farafontova E. P. Ecology: textbook. Yekaterinburg: Ural University Publishing House, 2016.
3. Makhkamova D. Central Asia and the countries of the East on the path of cooperation and dialogue of cultures. // Social opinion. Human rights. 2004. No. 2.
4. Zalesskaya, Yu.I. Managing the process of forming an individual's ecological culture / Yu.I. Zalesskaya // Kiravanne o' adukatsy. - 2008. - No. 4.
5. Yazdanov Z. Tendencies to restore and develop traditions of Uzbek folk ecologist culture. Philosophy doctor (RhD) dissertation and abstract. Tashkent: UzMU.
6. Mamashokirov S, Usmanov E. Ecologist security issues of sustainable development. -Tashkent: Science, 2009.
7. N. Smirnova, N. N. Moiseev. On political science and the future of humanity // Polis, 2008, No. 1.

